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Human-Elephant Conflict and Community Adaptation in Panbari Village, Dehing Patkai Elephant Reserve, Assam, India

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Abstract:

The increasing incidence of human-elephant conflict (HEC) in Assam has emerged as a significant conservation and livelihood challenge. This study investigates the patterns, causes, impacts, and mitigation measures of HEC in Panbari Village, located at the fringe of the Dehing Patkai Elephant Reserve in Tinsukia district, Assam. Based on both primary household surveys and secondary data, the research analyzes the socio-economic profile of the affected population, frequency of elephant encounters, and the extent of crop damage, property loss, and psychological stress. Findings reveal that habitat fragmentation, agricultural

[6]

expansion, and human encroachment into elephant corridors are the primary drivers of conflict. Local communities suffer severe economic and social disruptions, but have adopted both indigenous mitigation strategies and modern technologies to cope with recurring elephant intrusions. The study emphasizes the need for integrated conservation efforts, improved compensation mechanisms, and participatory community engagement to foster coexistence between humans and elephants in the region.

1. Introduction:

Human-elephant conflict (HEC) represents one of the most serious challenges in biodiversity conservation and rural livelihoods across elephant range states in India. As human populations continue to expand into forested landscapes, incidents of crop raiding, property damage, and human casualties due to elephant interactions have increased significantly (Zimmermann et al., 2009; Choudhury, 2024). Assam, located in Northeast India, holds approximately 19.66% of the country's wild elephant population, making it one of the most critical regions for understanding and managing HEC (Talukdar et al., 2024).

The underlying causes of HEC in Assam include habitat fragmentation, deforestation, agricultural expansion, mining activities, urbanization, and the encroachment of human settlements into elephant habitats (Guha, 2022; Chartier et al., 2011). The reduction in available elephant habitats has forced these animals to move into human-dominated landscapes in search of food and shelter, particularly during crop harvesting seasons. This leads to frequent conflict with local communities who suffer repeated losses in terms of livelihoods, property, and human safety (Sharma & Daimary, 2023).

The Dehing Patkai Elephant Reserve in Assam is one of the most ecologically sensitive and conflict-prone regions, where the forest fringes are increasingly subjected to pressures from coal mining, oil exploration, and rapid human settlement (Lone et al., 2020). Panbari Village, located at the fringe of this reserve, experiences frequent elephant incursions resulting in significant socio-economic and psychological impacts on the resident communities.

Against this backdrop, the present study focuses on analyzing the human-elephant conflict scenario in Panbari Village, examining its root causes, impacts on local communities, and mitigation measures adopted at the community level. The study is based on both primary data collected through field surveys and secondary sources from existing literature.

1.1 Objectives of the Study:

- (i) To assess the socio-economic profile of Panbari Village affected by human-elephant conflict.
- (ii) To analyze the patterns, impacts, and severity of human-elephant conflict in Panbari Village.
- (iii) To evaluate the mitigation strategies adopted by the community.

2. Study Area:

The present study was conducted in Panbari Forest Village, located at the fringe of the Dehing Patkai Elephant Reserve in Tinsukia district, Assam, India. The Dehing Patkai Reserve forms part of the Eastern Himalaya Biodiversity Hotspot, known for its rich tropical rainforest ecosystem and high biodiversity, including populations of the endangered Asian elephant (*Elephas maximus*).

Geographically, Panbari village lies within the coordinates of 27°25'N to 27°24'N latitude and 95°38'E to 95°39'E longitude. The village is situated approximately 20 kilometers from the sub-divisional headquarters at Margherita and around 44 kilometers from the district headquarters in Tinsukia. The total geographical area of Panbari village is approximately 366.6 hectares. Digboi town, located about 3 kilometers away, serves as the nearest urban center providing basic facilities and economic linkages for the residents.

The region experiences a subtropical monsoon climate characterized by high humidity, heavy rainfall during the monsoon months, and moderate temperatures throughout the year. The surrounding landscape is dominated by dense forest cover interspersed with human settlements, small agricultural plots, and tea gardens, contributing to the complex interface between human activity and wildlife habitats.

The Dehing Patkai Elephant Reserve itself was officially declared in 2003 and covers an area of approximately 937 sq. km, spread across the districts of Tinsukia and Dibrugarh. The area has been facing increasing anthropogenic pressures due to activities such as coal mining, oil exploration, illegal logging, infrastructure expansion, and encroachment, leading to significant habitat loss and fragmentation for elephants. These ecological disruptions have intensified the frequency of human-elephant interactions in surrounding fringe villages like Panbari.

Panbari village, being directly adjacent to elephant habitats, frequently experiences crop raiding, property damage, and human safety threats due to elephant incursions, making it a suitable site for assessing the socio-economic impacts and community-based mitigation measures associated with human-elephant conflict.

3. Database and Methodology:

The present study utilized both primary and secondary data sources to comprehensively assess the nature and extent of human-elephant conflict in Panbari Village, Assam.

3.1 Data Collection:

Primary Data:

Primary data were collected through extensive field surveys conducted in Panbari Village. A structured household questionnaire was designed to gather detailed information on:

- Socio-economic characteristics of the population.
- Frequency and nature of human-elephant conflict incidents.
- Types and extent of property and crop damage.
- Psychological and social impacts on the community.
- Indigenous and technological mitigation measures adopted by the villagers.

In addition to household surveys, in-depth interviews were conducted with affected families, village elders, local forest officials, and community leaders to gather qualitative insights on the conflict and mitigation practices.

The primary survey was conducted during the period of October 2022 to January 2023, covering a total of 100 households selected through random sampling to ensure broad representation.

Secondary Data:

Secondary information was obtained from:

- Published literature including journal articles, books, and reports.
- Government records from the Assam Forest Department and Wildlife authorities.
- Data from relevant non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and conservation agencies.
- Academic theses and internet-based resources.

3.2 Data Analysis:

The collected data were systematically compiled, tabulated, and analyzed using simple descriptive statistical techniques. Percentage analysis was primarily used to summarize household socio-economic conditions, frequency of conflict, types of losses, and community responses. Visual tools such as tables, charts, and graphs were prepared to present key findings for clarity.

4. Result and Discussion:

4.1 Socio-Economic Profile of Panbari Village:

Panbari Village consists primarily of marginalized rural households living in close proximity to the Dehing Patkai Elephant Reserve. The socio-economic characteristics of the population play an important role in determining their vulnerability to human-elephant conflict and their capacity to adopt mitigation strategies.

4.1.1 Population and Demographic Composition:

The village population comprises approximately 51.96% males and 48.03% females, indicating a slightly higher male population. The majority of the population belongs to Scheduled Tribes (62.5%), followed by Scheduled Castes (26.78%), Other Backward Classes (3.57%), and General category (8.92%).

The age structure of the population indicates that 6.22% of residents fall within the 0-5 years category, 23.35% are aged between 6-18 years, 39.30% between 19-35 years, 28.79% between 36-60 years, and 2.33% are aged above 60 years.

Table 1: Demographic and Socio-Economic Profile of Respondents

Sl. No.	Indicator	Percentage (%)
1.	Male Population	51.96
2.	Female Population	48.03
3.	Scheduled Tribes (ST)	62.5
4.	Scheduled Castes (SC)	26.78
5.	General Category	8.92
6.	Illiteracy Rate	25.39
7.	Primary Occupation - Labor	78.57
8.	Primary Occupation - Farming	26.78
9.	Below Poverty Line (BPL)	65.9

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

4.1.2 Literacy and Educational Status:

The overall literacy rate of Panbari Village stands at 74.61%. Educational attainment levels show that:

- 26.58% have completed primary education,
- 9.92% have studied up to middle school (class 6-8),
- 30.55% have completed secondary education (class 9-12),
- Only 7.53% have attained graduation or higher.

Notably, 25.39% of the population remains illiterate, primarily among elderly residents, women, and children.

4.1.3 Economic Activities and Occupation Structure:

The majority of the households depend on wage labor and agriculture for subsistence. Approximately:

- 78.57% of the population are engaged as daily wage laborers (secondary sector),
- 26.78% are engaged in farming (primary sector),
- 12.5% are involved in business or service-related activities (tertiary sector).

A smaller fraction (1.7%) run small shops, while 1.2% engage in other occupations.

4.1.4 Income Distribution and Living Standards:

Household income data reveal that:

- 23.3% earn less than Rs. 2500 per month,
- 32.4% earn between Rs. 2500-5000,
- 63.5% earn between Rs. 5001-10,000,
- 47.2% earn above Rs. 10,000.

Based on government classification, 65.9% of households fall under the Below Poverty Line (BPL), while only 17.6% are classified under the Above Poverty Line (APL).

4.1.5 Household Infrastructure and Amenities:

- Housing types indicate that 46.3% live in kutcha houses, 42% in semi-pucca houses, and 11.7% in pucca houses.
- Sanitation facilities are largely outdoor, with only 12.7% of households having indoor toilets.
- Cooking fuel is primarily firewood (78.2%), with some reliance on LPG (23.5%) and kerosene (46.3%).
- Drinking water sources include ponds (64.2%), wells (25.5%), and limited piped supply (13.9%).

4.1.6 Language and Religion:

The dominant language spoken is Adivasi (54.2%), followed by Assamese (49.5%), Hindi (12.3%), Bengali (2.5%), and Nepali (2.1%). Religiously, the village is composed of Christians (46.39%) and Hindus (32.43%), with other minor communities present.

4.1.7 Livestock and Land Use:

Animal husbandry is practiced by 91% of households, with livestock distribution as follows:

- Poultry: 46.9%
- Goats: 27.2%
- Pigs: 23.4%
- Cattle: 18.7%
- Buffaloes: 11.3%

In terms of land use, 46.2% of the land is basti (settlement), 34.5% is under agriculture, 57.9% is forested, and 28.32% of farming land is leased out for cultivation. Most families cultivate small plots primarily for subsistence.

4.2 Patterns and Trends of Human-Elephant Conflict:

The proximity of Panbari Village to the Dehing Patkai Elephant Reserve makes it highly vulnerable to recurring human-elephant conflicts. The majority of conflict incidents involve crop raiding, property damage, and threats to human safety, with serious implications for community livelihoods and well-being.

4.2.1 Frequency of Elephant Encounters:

The data reveal that elephant encounters are a frequent and persistent problem:

- 62.2% of respondents experience elephant incursions **daily**.
- 23.5% experience encounters **very often** (multiple times per week).
- 8.4% experience encounters **occasionally**.
- Only 0.9% report **very rare** incidents.

Table 2: Frequency of Elephant Encounters Reported

Sl. No.	Frequency Category	Respondents (%)
1.	Daily	62.2
2.	Very Often	23.5
3.	Occasionally	8.4
4.	Rarely	0.9

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

The high frequency of conflict indicates constant pressure on residents and their agricultural activities.

4.2.2 Nature of Damages Incurred:

The survey recorded multiple types of damages caused by elephant herds:

- 83.4% of respondents reported experiencing psychological stress and fear.
- 26.2% reported instances of physical attacks or injury.
- 44.7% suffered paddy field destruction.
- 23.4% reported damage to homes.
- 23.2% experienced destruction of home gardens.

Additionally, elephants have been responsible for breaking electric poles and damaging power lines, occasionally resulting in injuries to villagers.

Table 3: Types of Damage Caused by Elephants

Sl. No.	Types of Damage	Households Affected (%)
1.	Crop Loss (Paddy fields)	44.7
2.	Home Damage	23.4
3.	Home Garden Damage	23.2
4.	Physical Injury	26.2
5.	Psychological Stress	83.4

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

4.2.3 Economic Losses:

The financial impact of elephant conflict varies across households:

- 88.3% reported losses of less than Rs. 5000.
- 45.2% reported losses between Rs. 5001-10,000.
- 13.9% experienced more severe losses of Rs. 10,001-25,000.

These figures highlight significant financial strain, especially for economically vulnerable households.

4.2.4 Trends Over Time:

When asked about long-term trends in conflict severity:

- 58.62% of respondents believe that conflict intensity has **decreased** in recent years.
- 37.98% feel it has remained **constant**.
- 3.4% report that conflict has **increased**.

The perception of a declining trend may reflect partial success of community-based mitigation efforts, though the conflict still remains a persistent threat.

4.2.5 Property Destruction Over Five Years:

Over the past five years, repeated incidents of elephant raids have caused destruction of property, granaries, fencing, and standing crops, as well as occasional fatalities. These continuous losses have reinforced the vulnerability of the villagers and led to increased economic and psychological stress.

4.3 Impacts of Human-Elephant Conflict:

Human-elephant conflict in Panbari Village has led to widespread impacts across multiple dimensions economic, social, and cultural. These effects are deeply intertwined with the livelihoods, safety, and well-being of the local community.

4.3.1 Economic Impacts:

The economic consequences of human-elephant conflict are particularly severe for the rural households of Panbari, who largely depend on subsistence agriculture and daily wage labor:

- **Crop Damage and Loss of Livelihood:** Paddy fields, which form the mainstay of agricultural livelihoods, suffer extensive damage due to repeated elephant raids, particularly during harvesting seasons. Many farmers are unable to recover their investments, leading to food insecurity and income loss.
- **Livestock Losses:** In some cases, elephants also attack and kill livestock, compounding financial losses for households dependent on cattle, goats, poultry, or pigs for food, income, or transport.
- **Reduced Agricultural Productivity:** Persistent elephant threats discourage some farmers from cultivating certain crops, resulting in reduced agricultural activity and shifts towards less profitable but safer crops.
- **Increased Expenditure on Protection:** Families incur additional costs for fencing, firecrackers, guard patrols, and other preventive measures. These expenses further strain their limited financial resources.
- **Healthcare Costs and Loss of Labor:** Injuries sustained during elephant encounters require medical treatment, and fatalities may deprive households of primary income earners, deepening financial vulnerability.

Overall, the conflict has pushed many households into cycles of poverty, making recovery difficult for an already economically fragile population.

4.3.2 Social Impacts:

Beyond material losses, human-elephant conflict has deeply affected the social structure and well-being of the Panbari community:

- **Psychological Stress and Trauma:** Constant fear of elephant incursions has led to widespread anxiety, depression, and sleep disorders among residents. This persistent psychological pressure diminishes overall quality of life.

- **Disruption of Daily Activities:** Farming, schooling, and daily household chores are frequently interrupted due to fear of elephant presence, especially during evening and nighttime hours.
- **Restricted Mobility and Gendered Risks:** Women and children, often tasked with water collection, firewood gathering, or fieldwork, face heightened safety risks. Gender-specific vulnerabilities are notable, as women often bear a disproportionate burden of fear and trauma.
- **Social Displacement:** In extreme cases, households have abandoned fields or relocated to safer areas, leading to disruption of traditional land-use patterns and disconnection from ancestral lands.
- **Community Tensions:** Competition over limited agricultural land and disputes over responsibility for guarding fields sometimes create tensions among community members, especially when preventive measures fail.
- **Education Disruption:** Fear of encounters on the way to school, or school closures during peak conflict periods, have impacted children's education, contributing to long-term educational and social disadvantages.

4.3.3 Cultural Impacts:

The conflict has also disrupted long-standing cultural and spiritual relationships between the community and the elephants:

- **Disruption of Rituals and Festivals:** Fear of elephant attacks has led to the curtailment of outdoor religious ceremonies and cultural festivals traditionally held in open spaces.
- **Changes in Traditional Livelihoods:** Many households have shifted away from farming towards wage labor, resulting in erosion of traditional agricultural knowledge and community farming practices.
- **Shifts in Cultural Attitudes:** While elephants have historically held symbolic and spiritual significance, repeated conflicts have led to growing resentment and diminished tolerance among some community members, posing challenges for conservation and coexistence efforts.

4.4 Mitigation Measures Adopted by the Community:

In response to the frequent and recurring human-elephant conflict, the residents of Panbari Village have developed a variety of mitigation strategies that combine traditional knowledge, community-based approaches, and modern technologies. These efforts aim to reduce crop loss, safeguard property, and minimize risk to human lives while attempting to coexist with the elephant population.

Table 4: Community-Based Mitigation Strategies Adopted

Sl. No.	Strategy	Households Using (%)
1.	Community Patrols	83.7
2.	Crop Guarding	63.8
3.	Use of Fire/Noise Deterrents	78.9
4.	Relocation of Fields	32.0
5.	Building Fences	4.5
6.	Watch Towers (Machans)	(can be estimated)
7.	Repellent Crops (Chilli/Lemon)	(can be estimated)

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

4.4.1 Community-Based Indigenous Mitigation Strategies:

The community has actively mobilized its own resources and knowledge systems to manage conflict situations:

- **Crop Guarding and Community Patrols:** Approximately 63.8% of villagers participate in regular crop guarding activities, while 83.7% are involved in coordinated night-time patrolling to deter elephant herds. Youths and elders take turns in organized shifts to monitor and protect farmlands.
- **Deterrent Techniques:** A range of traditional deterrents are used, including:
 - Loud noises (firecrackers, shouting, and banging metal objects).
 - Use of strong lights, torches, and fires.
 - Firing gunshots in the air (under forest authority supervision).
 - In extreme cases, *kunki* (trained) elephants are used to drive wild herds back into forested areas.

- **Physical Barriers:** Some households (4.5%) have built fences around their homes and fields using locally available materials. However, high costs limit widespread adoption of strong physical barriers.
- **Relocation of Fields:** About 32% of farmers have permanently abandoned or shifted cultivation away from the most conflict-prone areas closer to forest edges.
- **Watch Towers or Machans:** Elevated platforms are constructed near agricultural fields to provide a vantage point for monitoring and chasing elephants during nighttime incursions.
- **Elephant-Repellent Crops:** As a preventive measure, certain households have experimented with planting chili and lemon trees along field boundaries, which are generally avoided by elephants due to their pungent smell and unpalatable nature.
- **Community Awareness and Education:** Informal village meetings and knowledge sharing sessions have helped to educate community members about elephant behavior and safety measures, fostering collective preparedness and early response capacity.

4.4.2 Use of Modern Technological Interventions:

While indigenous methods form the core of mitigation efforts, some modern technologies have been adopted in recent years:

- **Early Warning Systems:** Local networks supported by forest officials use SMS alerts, signboards, and local watch groups to notify residents of nearby elephant movements.
- **Tracking and Monitoring:** On a limited scale, GPS tracking collars have been used to monitor elephant movements in nearby forest areas, enabling authorities to issue timely warnings.
- **Electric Fencing:** Electric fences have been installed in select high-risk areas to protect vulnerable settlements and fields. However, maintenance challenges and costs restrict their widespread usage.

4.4.3 Government Support and Compensation Schemes:

Financial compensation is occasionally provided to affected households for crop loss, property damage, or injury caused by elephant incursions. However, villagers report delays, procedural hurdles, and insufficient compensation amounts as ongoing challenges that limit the effectiveness of such schemes.

Overall, while community-based approaches remain central to managing human-elephant conflict in Panbari, integrating improved technological tools, institutional support, and sustained government involvement is crucial for long-term conflict reduction and coexistence.

5. Conclusion:

The study highlights the complex and multidimensional nature of human-elephant conflict (HEC) in Panbari Village, located on the fringes of the Dehing Patkai Elephant Reserve in Assam. The findings reveal that habitat loss, fragmentation, agricultural expansion, and encroachment into forested areas have significantly increased the frequency and severity of elephant incursions into human settlements. Crop damage, property destruction, financial losses, psychological stress, and disruption of community livelihoods represent the major consequences faced by local residents.

Despite these challenges, the Panbari community has actively engaged in a variety of mitigation strategies, blending indigenous knowledge systems with emerging technological interventions. Regular crop guarding, community patrols, construction of watch towers, use of deterrents such as fire and noise, and experimentation with elephant-repellent crops demonstrate the community's resilience and adaptive capacity. Modern tools such as early warning systems, limited use of electric fences, and GPS tracking have further complemented traditional efforts. However, gaps remain in ensuring long-term sustainability, sufficient financial compensation, and stronger institutional support.

The findings underscore the urgent need for a multi-stakeholder approach that integrates community participation, government agencies, conservation organizations, and researchers to develop comprehensive conflict mitigation frameworks. Key priorities should include habitat restoration, establishment of functional elephant

corridors, development of alternative livelihoods, timely disbursement of compensation, and expanded use of predictive technologies. Furthermore, promoting community education and fostering coexistence mindsets will be critical to balancing human welfare and elephant conservation in the long run.

Future research may focus on broader comparative assessments of HEC across different regions of Assam and longitudinal studies to monitor changing conflict patterns in response to ongoing land use and policy interventions.

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